

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Sobuddinov Soxibjon

**THE INTERACTION BETWEEN THE PRODUCT TO BE GROUND
AND THE GRINDING BLADE IN THE GRINDING CHAMBER**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUN

HONORED
MENTION

YOUR
SEAL